

SITE GS/SPHINX	DATE 6/30/79	AREA NE	SQUARE N2/W1-E1	PAGE
	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top: 10.68	Bottom: 10.61 10.59 <small>Small Hole</small>
	DIMENSIONS			
Diameter:	Width: 22-36 cm	Length: 1.63 m	Depth: 8-10 cm deepest	

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions	
1	Gypsum SAND Mix	Yellowish to light Buff	Very Hard. Packed	Rubbly	T lightly embedded surface	Lm ✓ FRAGS	Gp
						Gr	Char
					D	Do	
						Ba	
					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
					D	Do	
						Ba	
					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
					D	Do	
						Ba	
					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
					D	Do	
						Ba	
					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
					D	Do	
						Ba	
					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
					D	Do	
						Ba	

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/ 2 No./ 13, 14	B&W: Roll/ 2 No./ 9, 10
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DRAWN	Area Plan: 1:20	Feature Plan:	Sections: 1:10 section w. Fc18
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: Perhaps associated w. Fc18. Some of fill taken out may be poor quality yellowish ferruginous natural rock. Small hole - 2cm diam - End artificial?

A "drag" mark for block moved assoc. with Fc18?